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ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN BUSINESS ACROSS SECONDARY, TERTIARY, AND QUATERNARY SECTORS

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Abstract

Within the Romanian economic landscape, a shift is observed as the primary and secondary sectors experience a decline in value, countered by substantial growth in the tertiary and quaternary sectors, particularly within the services domain. This paper centers its hypotheses on leveraging the potential of Romanian mountainous regions for the advancement of specific sectors. A strategic blend of secondary, tertiary, and quaternary sectors with agriculture emerges as a focal point. The emphasis lies on catalyzing Information and Communication Technology (ICT) development, fostering the clustering of evolved and emerging industries such as textiles and wood, and intensifying food processing and agro-food production. The integration

of these elements aims to spur holistic development, with a keen focus on the unique opportunities offered by Romania's mountainous terrain.

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Keywords: mountain entrepreneurship, mountain theoretical approach, mountain science

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Introduction:

Romania's mountainous regions, adorned with natural beauty, have become more than just picturesque landscapes. They serve as the backdrop for a burgeoning business environment that spans the secondary, tertiary, and quaternary sectors. This article embarks on an exploration of how entrepreneurial endeavors in these sectors have evolved against the breathtaking backdrop of Romanian mountains. (Covaci B & Covaci M, 2021a-h; Covaci M & Covaci B, 2021a-h)

The Ascendance of Mountain Entrepreneurship:

In recent years, Romania has witnessed a notable surge in economic activities nestled within its mountainous terrains. The secondary sector, encompassing industries and manufacturing, has seen a steady rise.

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Simultaneously, the tertiary sector, focused on services, and the quaternary sector, involving knowledge-based activities, have experienced significant growth.

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Challenges and Opportunities:

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While the ascent in mountain entrepreneurship is evident, it is essential to acknowledge the challenges and opportunities inherent in this unique business landscape. The idyllic setting presents an enticing canvas, but it also poses challenges, especially for the primary sector, which sometimes takes a backseat in the pursuit of progress.

Ensuring sustainable and quality food production becomes a critical concern, demanding careful consideration from public governance. The delicate balance between economic development and environmental preservation requires strategic solutions that foster collaboration across sectors.

Sectors Under the Lens:

This article scrutinizes various sectors within Romania's mountain business environment, providing insights into their dynamics:

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- Industry, Construction, and Services (Ix): An amalgamation of diverse activities forming the backbone of mountain entrepreneurship.

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- Wholesale and Retail Trade; Repair of Motor Vehicles and Motorcycles (Ix1): Examining the commerce and repair activities that contribute to the economic tapestry.

6

- Professional, Scientific, and Technical Activities; Administrative and Support Activities (Ix2): Delving into the knowledge-based services that thrive in mountainous regions.

- Transport and Storage (Ix5): Unveiling the logistics and transportation intricacies crucial for connectivity in mountainous terrain.

- Accommodation and Food Services (Ix7): Exploring the hospitality and culinary ventures that capitalize on the region's allure.

- Information and Communication (Ix8): Analyzing the role of technology and communication in fostering mountain business.

- Education, Human Health, and Social Assistance (Ix9): Understanding the contributions of educational and healthcare services to mountain communities.

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- Financial and Insurance Activities; Real Estate Activities (Ix10): Investigating the financial and real estate dimensions shaping the mountain business landscape.

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Results:

The ascent of mountain entrepreneurship finds support in significant investments dedicated to the development of mountainous areas and initiatives aimed at repopulating these regions. Within the European Union, mountainous terrains are recognized for their immense potential in organic farming and contributions to human health. The air-water-soil ecosystem in these areas is perceived as less polluted compared to other topographical landscapes. The legislative framework specific to mountain areas, a unique feature within Europe, reflects the importance Europeans attribute to sustainable mountain science as a driver of economic development.

The conviction in the potential of mountain entrepreneurship, particularly in terms of employability, is a recurring theme in studies and applications,
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drawing the attention of both public and corporate governance in European countries.

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The author asserts that the agri-food industry is pivotal for Romania's future, aligning with studies predicting an unprecedented agri-food crisis (Zaman et al., 2013; Benaki et al., 2007). This paper offers solutions tailored to Romania's dynamics, utilizing Eurostat indices on business demography for a comprehensive analysis.

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Employing the Eurostat classification, the paper conducts an in-depth examination of industry, services, and the quaternary sector within the broader sector of Industry, Construction, and Services, excluding insurance activities (encompassing secondary, tertiary, and quaternary sectors). The results, processed using SPSS, are derived from the authors' calculations based on Eurostat data, as presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Active enterprises in the mountainous area of Romania - Secondary, tertiary and quaternary sectors (except agriculture)

Source: Eurostat - Business Demography Statistics

For the computation, the researchers utilized eight variables spanning the years 2008-2018, with SPSS recognizing and validating all data points (no data invalidations were recorded). The constituent sub-sectors witnessed substantial growth during the examined period (2008-2018), showcasing increases as follows: Ix1 by 132.95%, Ix2 by 182.56%, Ix3 by 134.26%, Ix4 by 134.13%, Ix5 by 220.71%, Ix6 by 441.63%, Ix7 by 180.84%, Ix8 by 226.81%, Ix9 by 326.02%, and Ix10 by 183.50% (refer to Figure 2).

Figure 2. The variation in the period 2008 - 2018 of the constituent sub-sectors for secondary, tertiary and quaternary sectors

Source: Eurostat - Business Demography Statistics

The observed elevation signifies a continuous upward trajectory in the mountainous business environment across Romania's secondary, tertiary, and quaternary sectors, occasionally at the expense of the primary sector. As ensuring food provision, especially of high quality, remains a paramount global and national concern, public governance should address this by formulating solutions that foster the concurrent development of the primary sector in close coordination with other sectors.

Conclusion:

As Romania's mountain business continues its ascent across secondary, tertiary, and quaternary sectors, it becomes a testament to the adaptability and resilience of entrepreneurial endeavors in these awe-inspiring landscapes. Navigating the heights of economic development while preserving the intrinsic beauty of the mountains requires a strategic vision that harmonizes progress with environmental stewardship. In the tapestry of Romanian mountain business, each sector weaves a unique thread, contributing to the diverse and vibrant economic portrait painted against the backdrop of majestic peaks.

The study encompasses the following sectors:

- Industry, construction, and services, excluding insurance activities of companies (Ix);
- Wholesale and retail trade; repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles (Ix1);
- Professional, scientific and technical activities; administrative and support activities (Ix2);
- Industry (excluding construction) (Ix3);
- Constructions (Ix4);

- Transport and storage (Ix5);
- Arts, entertainment, and recreation; other service activities (Ix6);
- Accommodation and food services (Ix7);
- Information and communication (Ix8);
- Education, human health, and social assistance (Ix9);
- Financial and insurance activities; real estate activities, excluding companies (Ix10).

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WORLD CONTEXTS OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP, AS SUPPORT FOR SPECIFIC ECONOMIC CONTEXTS OF MOUNTAIN INVESTMENTS

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Abstract

Exploring the nuances of entrepreneurship necessitates a deep dive into the prevailing economic landscape, with a specific focus on mountainous regions. The dynamics of self-employment manifest with greater prominence in less economically developed countries and regions, where the informal sector and illegitimate practices exert a dominant influence on labor markets and production organization. These areas typically grapple with challenges such as ineffective monitoring, reporting, and tracing mechanisms, which, in turn, may contribute to a dearth of new companies showcasing genuine development potential. Particularly in countries characterized by vast mountainous terrains and elevated poverty levels, there arises an imperative need for global investments.

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In the context of low investment areas, such as mountain regions, a multitude of innovative concepts may emerge and penetrate the market through successful informal enterprises. These ventures might even burgeon into integral components of value chains, albeit without legal registration. Despite their revenue-generating capacities, unregistered businesses remain excluded from official reporting channels, notably in national accounts, thus fostering an underground economy. This phenomenon is especially prevalent in mountainous areas, where the challenging operational conditions, surpassing those in other topographical settings, compel mountain entrepreneurs to engage in the clandestine economic activities of a country. In nations with inadequately safeguarded economies, mountainous regions often witness the proliferation of the underground economy, a consequence of limited protections and insufficient incentives for entrepreneurs. This scenario gives rise to a spectrum of economic activities ranging from black and gray to informal and illegal, as elucidated by Desai (2017).

A comprehensive global investigation, encompassing countries eager to participate, undertook an adult population survey (PHC) as part of the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM) initiative. The Adult Population Survey (APS), administered to a minimum of 2000 adults in each

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participating country, serves as an intricate questionnaire designed to gather exhaustive insights into entrepreneurship, encompassing the attitudes and aspirations of respondents. The outcomes of this expansive study unveil compelling statistics shedding light on the intricacies of entrepreneurship and innovation within a given country. The interplay between economic contexts, entrepreneurship, and mountain investments becomes increasingly evident as we delve into the multifaceted layers of this research endeavor.

(figure 1)

Figure 1. Percentage of those involved in TEA - business services sector: information and communications, financial and real estate intermediation, professional or administrative services, as defined by ISIC 4.0

Source: <https://www.gemconsortium.org/data>

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The statistics are presented as a percentage (%), in relation to the maximum potential of 100%. At European level, Western and Nordic countries are showing good results in the sustainability of entrepreneurship, not necessarily through the establishment of new businesses, but rather through the development of existing ones. The situation is different in the countries of South-Eastern Europe. Thus, in Romania, the perceived opportunities are 33.30 percent (the proportion in which respondents consider that there are certain entrepreneurial opportunities); Perceived capabilities 46.30 (represents the percentage of existence of entrepreneurial capacity); Fear of failure 40.50; Entrepreneurial intentions 29.00; Entrepreneurial activities in the early stages - total (TEA) 10.80; Commercial property 7.50; Entrepreneurial activity of employees 4.60; Motivation index 1.20; TEA - Women / Men 0.50; TEA - opportunities developed by Women / Men 1.10; High job creation expectations 39.80; Innovation 30.00; Business Sector related to services 17.60; Successful entrepreneurs 75.10; Entrepreneurship - career option 72.40.

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The indicators replicated in the other European countries that report entrepreneurial statistics are:

- Austria: 31.20; 53.30; 36.80; 4.10; 6.20; 7.80; 7.00; 0.80; 0.50; 36.60; 79.80; 44.50.

- Croatia: 47.20; 75.00; 52.10; 24.30; 12.70; 4.20; 7.70; 0.60; 21.50; 33.70; 53.50; 59.30.

- Cyprus: 21.10; 58.10; 49.10; 20.50; 8.50; 7.30; 6.40; 0.60; 32.70; 41.00; 70.70; 76.70.

- Germany: 36.00; 47.60; 31.00; 10.70; 4.80; 6.20; 5.90; 0.90; 24.90; 29.80; 81.80; 54.90.

- Greece: 27.90; 53.20; 53.10; 11.30; 8.60; 14.60; 2.50; 0.60; 12.70; 17.50; 70.30; 69.50.

- Italy: 62.20; 60.80; 28.40; 4.50; 1.90; 2.20; 1.10; 0.30; 2.30; 23.40.

- Latvia: 37.10; 55.30; 41.60; 17.20; 15.60; 11.10; 3.50; 0.60; 29.80; 21.20; 61.80; 56.70.

- Luxembourg: 41.90; 45.70; 42.30; 11.10; 8.00; 3.60; 4.50; 0.50; 34.00; 43.60.

- Netherlands: 48.80; 43.60; 38.20; 13.10; 11.50; 7.00; 1.70; 0.70; 13.50; 41.20.

- Norway: 57.00; 41.60; 27.40; 5.60; 7.60; 4.10; 4.90; 0.50; 28.40; 41.80.

- Poland: 51.60; 60.00; 41.20; 4.70; 3.10; 12.20; 1.40; 0.60; 21.60; 25.40; 60.10; 59.90.
- Russia: 33.40; 34.50; 46.50; 8.30; 8.50; 4.70; 0.40; 0.70; 43.30; 17.10; 72.50; 75.30.
- Slovakia: 40.90; 56.40; 48.70; 13.80; 13.80; 6.50; 3.40; 0.50; 28.80; 33.80; 62.10; 49.30.
- Slovenia: 42.00; 59.40; 43.80; 11.90; 6.00; 7.00; 6.50; 0.70; 24.70; 22.70; 85.10; 68.70.
- Spain: 16.50; 51.90; 53.60; 6.80; 5.20; 6.70; 1.30; 0.90; 8.70; 30.80; 61.10; 56.70.
- Sweden: 62.50; 52.10; 42.80; 8.30; 7.30; 6.00; 6.10; 0.50; 15.70; 34.40.
- Switzerland: 26.70; 44.50; 33.40; 7.30; 9.20; 6.70; 7.30; 0.90; 9.50; 33.60; 71.90; 49.30.
- Great Britain: 27.30; 54.50; 48.30; 8.20; 7.80; 6.50; 6.50; 0.70; 16.40; 26.40; 77.10; 69.60.

The indicators of entrepreneurial behavior and attitudes measured by the Adult Population Survey (PHC) take into account:

- Perceived opportunity rate: Percentage of the population 18-64 (people involved in any stage of entrepreneurial activity, exclusively) who see good opportunities to start a company in the area where they live.

- Perceived capacity rate: Percentage of the population 18-64 (people involved in any stage of entrepreneurial activity, exclusively) who consider that they have the skills and knowledge needed to start a business.
- Fear of failure: Percentage of the population 18-64 (people involved in any stage of entrepreneurial activity, exclusively) who are afraid of failure in setting up a business.
- Rate of entrepreneurial intentions: Percentage of the population 18-64 (people involved in any stage of entrepreneurial activity, exclusively) with latent entrepreneurs and who intend to start a business within three years.
- Total rate of entrepreneurial activity in the early stages (TEA): Percentage of the population 18-64 who present either a developing entrepreneur or owner-manager of a new business.
- Current rate of business owners: Percentage of the population 18-64 who is currently the owner-manager of an established business, ie owns and manages functional businesses - pays salaries or makes any other payments for more than 42 months.
- Employee entrepreneurship rate: The rate of employee involvement in entrepreneurial activities, such as the development or launch of new goods or services, or the establishment of a new business unit, a new unit or a subsidiary.

- Motivational index: the percentage of those involved in ASD who are motivated by opportunities.

- TEA ratio between women and men: the percentage of the population aged 18-64 who is either an incipient entrepreneur or an owner-manager of a “new business”, divided by the equivalent percentage for their male counterparts.

- TEA opportunity ratio for women / men: The percentage of women involved in TEA and i) who say they can't find another job option, respectively (ii) who indicate that the main determinant of being involved in this opportunity is independence or growth their income, rather than maintaining income, divided by the percentage equivalent to their male counterparts.

- Expectation rate for job creation: Percentage of those involved in ASD who expect to create 6 or more jobs in 5 years.

- Innovation rate: The percentage of those involved in TEA that indicates that their product or service is new to at least some customers and that few companies offer the same product.

- Business services sector rate: Percentage of those involved in TEA in the “Business services” sector - information and communication, financial and real estate intermediation, professional or administrative services, as defined by ISIC 4.0.

- Success rate of entrepreneurs: Percentage of the population 18-64 who agree with the statement that in their country, successful entrepreneurs are in large numbers and have increased benefits.

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- Entrepreneurship as a high career choice rate: The percentage of 18-64 people who agree with the statement that in their country most people consider starting a business as a timely career choice.

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(<https://www.gemconsortium.org/data>)

According to statistics and qualitative studies conducted in the mountainous areas of Europe, independent activities are encountered in the countries of the South-East. The establishment of new companies and entrepreneurship at an early stage are ambivalent phenomena - sustainable in Western and Nordic countries, with a low degree of sustainability in the South-East. Necessity entrepreneurship is very common in all mountain areas, the vast majority of mountain businesses being set up as a result of a clear need, otherwise the failure of entrepreneurs is guaranteed. Opportunity entrepreneurship is rare in the mountainous areas of Europe, and it is used only in the case of a high opportunity such as the organization of championships in those areas, large-scale events, etc.

The paper represents a part of the Covaci, B. (2021), PhD (c) research report 1, Oradea University

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ENTREPRENEURIAL ENDEAVORS IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAINS: INDUSTRY, CONSTRUCTION, AND SERVICES

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Abstract

The document outlines the entrepreneurial landscape in the Romanian mountains, focusing on the economic sectors of industry, construction, and services. It highlights a crucial turning point in the upward trajectory of mountainous Romania, emphasizing the prominence of the secondary economic sector in the initial phase (2000-2007) and the subsequent dominance of the tertiary/quaternary sectors in the latter part (2008-2018), at the expense of the primary economic sector. Notably, services, particularly those related to summer sales and entertainment, thrive on increased capital inflow during the summer season, driven by the return of emigrants to Romania. The elevated fluctuation in the active enterprise population signifies the pronounced volatility of the mountain economy in Romania. During the latter part of 2008-2018, the economy diversified its

development, relying on additional resources such as information and communication technology (ICT) and food production.

Keywords: mountain entrepreneurship, economic sectors, mountain statistic

Production does not represent much of the industry and services in mountainous Romania, the regional strategy must be based on facilities for the production sectors. In this context, agriculture should not be neglected and agricultural products should be processed locally for the secondary, tertiary and quaternary sectors. Processed products must be distributed at higher prices than primary products, thus adding value to primary production.

The statistics for Industry, constructions and services, except for the insurance activities of the companies (figure 1 - panels a-az), present for each indicator ascending values for average and median, the other statistical indicators having antagonistic fluctuations sometimes (repeated repetitively at each indicator), as follows:

I1 - Average of 226349.9, Error Std. average 13997.8, Median 246416.0, Deviation Std. 46425.5, Skewness -0.9, Kurtosis -0.8, Variation 130479.0, Minimum 144988.0, Maximum 275467.0, Percentile 50 Value 246416.0; I2

- 27335.5, 3339.0, 27931.0, 11074.3, 1.3, 3.9, 43287.0, 11498.0, 54785.0,
27931.0;

I3 - 24347.6, 2998.4, 21223.0, 8995.2, 0.9, -0.5, 25258.0, 14128.0, 39386.0,
21223.0;

I4 - 16094.4, 1111.2, 15179.0, 3685.4, 2.1, 5.4, 12744.0, 13181.0, 25925.0,
15179.0;

I5 - 543.3, 83.8, 433.0, 277.9, 2.1, 4.7, 1014.0, 251.0, 1265.0, 433.0;

I6 - 1237614.3, 25923.3, 1235524.0, 85977.8, -0.7, 0.2, 277991.0,
1065478.0, 1343469.0, 1235524.0;

I7 - 1123610.9, 17809.7, 1096497.0, 59068.2, 0.9, 0.8, 214040.0,
1035313.0, 1249353.0, 1096497.0;

I8 - 50229.1, 3907.9, 48456.0, 12960.9, 1.6, 4.4, 51147.0, 31967.0, 83114.0,
48456.0;

I9 - 33040.1, 1552.5, 32659.0, 5149.1, 0.7, 0.4, 17498.0, 25891.0, 43389.0,
32659.0;

I10 - 36132.2, 2920.1, 34212.0, 8760.2, 0.6, -1.5, 23072.0, 26850.0,
49922.0, 34212.0;

I11 - 19691.1, 2969.1, 16786.0, 8907.3, 1.4, 1.6, 26260.0, 12509.0, 38769.0,
16786.0;

I12 - 53431.8, 2999.4, 50805.0, 9947.8, 1.4, 1.4, 33207.0, 41409.0, 74616.0,
50805.0;

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I13 - 34240.0, 1443.9, 33703.0, 4788.9, 0.9, 0.4, 15262.0, 28577.0, 43839.0, 33703.0;

I14 - 6.2, 5.5, 2.1, 17.5, 2.7, 8.0, 64.1, -10.0, 54.1, 2.1;

I15 - 23.4, 2.4, 19.9, 7.1, 1.3, 1.2, 21.3, 16.9, 38.2, 19.9;

I16 - 11.9, 1.2, 11.3, 3.9, 2.1, 5.6, 14.3, 7.9, 22.2, 11.3;

I17 - 11.0, 1.5, 8.5, 4.6, 0.7, -1.5, 12.1, 5.8, 18.0, 8.5;

I18 - 72.2, 9.7, 62.5, 27.3, 1.1, -0.4, 67.8, 47.3, 115.1, 62.5;

I19 - 7.3, 0.5, 6.8, 1.7, 0.4, -1.3, 4.7, 5.2, 10.0, 6.8;

I20 - 4.1, 0.3, 3.9, 1.0, 2.0, 5.4, 3.9, 2.8, 6.8, 3.9;

I21 - 2.0, 0.1, 1.8, 0.5, 1.9, 4.5, 1.7, 1.5, 3.3, 1.8;

I22 - 68.0, 3.8, 65.8, 12.7, -0.3, 0.5, 45.0, 42.3, 87.3, 65.8;

I23 - 2.9, 0.3, 2.6, 0.8, 0.9, -0.8, 2.3, 2.1, 4.4, 2.6;

I24 - 1.6, 0.1, 1.4, 0.4, 0.7, -0.9, 1.0, 1.2, 2.1, 1.4;

I25 - 55.4, 3.1, 54.1, 10.2, 1.5, 3.3, 38.3, 42.2, 80.6, 54.1;

I26 - 4.3, 0.2, 4.1, 0.8, 0.7, -0.3, 2.5, 3.4, 5.8, 4.1;

I27 - 2.4, 0.1, 2.5, 0.4, -1.9, 4.7, 1.4, 1.5, 2.9, 2.5.

The values presented show that the secondary, tertiary and quaternary sectors have a good development in Romania for indicators I1-2, I4-5, I7-16, I20-21 and I25. Indicators I3, I6, I17-19, I22-24 and I26-27 also show negative values, the general picture showing a good and problematic general mountain entrepreneurial situation for the employment rate, as well as for

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the survival rate of enterprises after three years from establishment. This reflects the employment rate and survival rate of enterprises in the mountain area the general situation in Romania, which has been steadily declining in recent years. According to the National Institute of Statistics in 2020 (trend valid for the last four years), the employment rate of the working age population (15-64 years) was 65.6%, down from the previous year by 0, 2 percentage points. In 2020, the employment rate * of the population aged 20-64 was 70.8%, with 0.8 percentage points above the national target of 70% set in the context of the Europe 2020 Strategy. In 2020 the active population of Romania was 8973 thousand people, of which 8521 thousand were employed and 452 thousand were unemployed” (INS, 2021a).

The same trend is found in the disbanded enterprises, in 2019 “the one-year survival rate of enterprises being over 60%. The proportion of those who have definitively ceased their activity is 4.8%, decreasing by 2.4 percentage points compared to the previous year, and the share of enterprises still inactive one year after the establishment is around 29.0%” (INS, 2021b).

Businesses within active enterprises in the secondary, tertiary and quaternary sectors (except the agriculture sector) can represent Romania's development engine. The multitude of active enterprises, but especially the quality and the added value they give to the local economy leads to the increase of the living standard and the well-being of the population. In this

sense, governmental actions are required, but especially local, in order to develop entrepreneurship. A considerable potential is represented by the mountain area, where the primary products have a high quality value. The local and central measures developed must take into account some of the results of this study.

Panels a – I1, b – I2, c – I3, d – I4, e – I5, f – I6, g – I7, h – I8, i – I9

Panels j – I10, k – I11, l – I12, m – I13, n – I14, o – I15, p – I16, q – I17, r – I18

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Panels s – I19, t – I20, u – I21, v – I22, w – I23, x – I24, y – I25, z – I26, az – I27

Figure 1 Histograms for secondary, tertiary and quaternary sectors for the indicators I1-I27 (2008-2018)

Source: Author according to Eurostat

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The central trend of the secondary, tertiary and quaternary sectors of the economy in the analyzed period shows that the population of active enterprises in mountainous Romania increased considerably from 2008 to 2018. The statistics related to this indicator show a high degree of non-variability, which means that the results they show a large deviation and are positive. The corresponding symmetrical distributions lead to the idea that the business environment begins to stabilize considerably in the analyzed period. Kurtosis with a low standard error is a congestion in some industries, ICT being specific to Romania.

Even though agriculture is still the most important part of the economy, industry and services have grown considerably in volume, which positively influences the number of enterprises in the population.

Indicators for which the study is performed:

- Active business population - number (I1)
- Newly established businesses - number (I2)
- Abolition of businesses in t - number (I3)
- Newly established enterprises in t-3 that have survived to t - number (I4)

- Enterprises with high employment growth (increase of 10% or more) - number (I5)
- Persons employed in enterprises active in t - number (I6)
- Employed in enterprises active in t - number (I7)
- Persons engaged in business established in t - number (I8)
- Employees in businesses established in t - number (I9)
- Persons engaged in business abolished in t - number (I10)
- Employees in businesses dissolved in t - number (I11)
- Persons employed in enterprises newly established in t-3 who have survived to t - number (I12)
- Persons employed in the year of establishment in enterprises newly established in t-3 who have survived to t - number (I13)
- Net business growth - percentage (I14)
- Net business situation: establishment rate + dissolution rate - percentage (I15)
- Establishment rate: number of enterprises established in the reference period (t) divided by the number of enterprises active in t - percentage (I16)
- Dissolution rate: number of enterprises disbanded in the reference period (t) divided by the number of enterprises active in t - percentage (I17)

- 3-year survival rate: number of enterprises in the reference period (t) newly established in t-3 that survived to t divided by the number of enterprises established in t-3 - percentage (I18)
- Share of enterprises aged 3 years in the business population - percentage (I19)
- Employment rate of start-ups: number of persons employed in the reference period (t) among start-ups in t, divided by the number of persons employed in t in the total number of active enterprises - percentage (I20)
- Average size of start-ups: number of persons employed in the reference period (t) among start-ups in t, divided by the number of start-ups in t (I21)
- Rate of new employees paid in enterprises: number of employees in the reference period (t) of newly established enterprises in t, divided by the number of persons employed in t in enterprises newly established in t - percentage (I22)
- Employment rate in disbanded enterprises: number of persons employed in the reference period (t) within the disbanded enterprises divided by the number of persons employed in t in enterprises active in t - percentage (I23)
- Enterprise growth rate of three years: number of persons employed in the reference period (t) in newly established enterprises in t-3, which survived to t, divided by the number of persons employed in t -3 by the same companies, a percentage growth rate - percentage (I24)

- Employment rate of enterprises older than 3 years: number of persons employed in newly established enterprises in t-3 who survived in t, divided by the number of persons employed in active enterprises - percentage (I25)
- Share of high-growth enterprises in employment: number of high-growth enterprises divided by the number of active enterprises with at least 10 employees - percentage (I26)
- Share of enterprises with measured increased growth in employment: number of enterprises with increased growth divided by the number of active enterprises with at least 10 employees - percentage (I27).

The paper represents a part of the Covaci, B. (2021), PhD (c) research report 1, Oradea University

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PROFESSIONAL, SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL, ADMINISTRATIVE AND SUPPORT OF THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN ACTIVITIES

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Abstract

The economic incentives that shape academic entrepreneurship are affected by the institutional characteristics of national university systems. These institutional characteristics do not affect the intensity of patenting and business creation activities. Rather, they explain the extent to which business activities may or may not help scientific entrepreneurs progress in their careers. Among these institutional features, the autonomy of the university, the mobility of staff and the principle of the principal investigator stand out as the most prominent.

Keywords: Romanian mountain activities; mountain statistic; professional, scientific and technical, administrative and support

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A study about the emergence of entrepreneurship as a field of research indicated that researchers in Anglo-Saxon countries have dominated the field for the past 20 years. The relatively strong impact of the Nordic and Netherlands countries is noteworthy. Using bibliographic coupling as a new bibliometric technique, five distinct clusters of knowledge from the entrepreneurial research literature were noted. The first cluster contains works focused on the cognitive aspects of entrepreneurship. A second related cluster includes works that elucidate the demographic and personality determinants of entrepreneurship. A third very homogeneous cluster consists primarily of conceptual works that study the origins, processes and impact of entrepreneurship. A fourth cluster deals with entrepreneurial financing and governance arrangements in new projects. The final and most heterogeneous cluster contains works that investigate topics ranging from networks and alliances; the strategies used by new businesses to gain a competitive advantage; to entry strategies designed to target international markets. A very strong relationship was observed between the first and the third group of works, an indicative finding of the conceptual nature of the works in both groups. The research results show the need for a more detailed analysis of the structure of knowledge in the field of entrepreneurship to identify smaller, emerging or disappearing topics in that

rapidly growing literature (<https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/30704637.pdf>).

(Meyer et al., 2014)

Technology transfer based on patents and spin-offs is largely the product of a specific institutional history, that of US research universities, where these characteristics have been prominent. Each introduction of these issues into the various European university systems requires first of all strong reflections and adjustments that take into account the institutional, organizational and environmental characteristics of academic research at national level. University entrepreneurs working in patenting, the establishment of companies (and more generally in technology transfer) come disproportionately from among scientific entrepreneurs with a brilliant scientific history, possibly oriented towards basic research. The economic agenda of these scientists focuses on the entrepreneurial efforts of the university, designed to gain reputation by building discipline, creating and managing laboratories and research teams, and the appetite for economic resources needed to achieve these goals (Franzoni, Chiara & Lissoni, Francesco (2006). Academic entrepreneurship, patents, and spin-offs: critical issues and lessons for Europe).

A study that highlighted the ways in which managers manage the social ambivalence of scientists working in new publicly managed research organizations underscores the relative importance of managers' behaviors
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and actions on scientists' entrepreneurial behaviors in addressing sociological ambivalence. for practice. Clear and explicit management strategies to encourage the pursuit of marketing opportunities and results demonstrate the agenda of top-down approaches to organizational change and results. The success of innovation and its implementation in the public sector is based on the skills of managers to obtain the necessary entrepreneurial behaviors. Due to the many and complex tensions surrounding public sector management and science, management must create, as far as possible, an organizational context that supports and supports "entrepreneurial" scientists. Through this study, practices aimed at identifying and managing these "entrepreneurial" types and stimulating less entrepreneurial types become a key consideration for the performance of entrepreneurs. By addressing the cognitive conflicts and "border work" of these scientists, the managers of these CRIs reduce the tensions and conflicts that arise around the new institutional and social structures. These answers are necessarily based on the normative acceptance of the professional scientific team and on the compensatory institutional and historical trajectories of the institutions ([https://researchbank.swinburne.edu.au/file/f81f47bd-089c-4831-b4ac-08edb612de77/1/PDF% 20% 28Published% 20version% 29.pdf](https://researchbank.swinburne.edu.au/file/f81f47bd-089c-4831-b4ac-08edb612de77/1/PDF%20%28Published%20version%29.pdf)).

The studies of Krabel et al. highlights two main results that spring from their empirical analysis (Internationalization of science and its influence on academic entrepreneurship). First of all, mobility is conducive to scientific entrepreneurship. Evidence suggests that foreign nationality and foreign education both predict the likelihood of being an entrepreneur in the face. Second, our results show that a certain subpopulation of scientists is commercially active and that entrepreneurship is most likely to occur within this subpopulation. Human capital, business experience - as inventions or the founding of companies - and perceptions that the commercialization of science is common or reputable are important factors influencing scientific entrepreneurship (Krabel, Stefan; Siegel, Donald S .; Slavtchev, Viktor (2009): The internationalization of science and its influence on academic entrepreneurship, Jena Economic Research Papers, No. 2009,026, Friedrich Schiller University Jena and Max Planck Institute of Economics, Jena <https://www.econstor.eu/bitstream/10419/31781/1/59777191X.PDF>).

Statistics for Professional, Scientific and Technical Activities; administrative and support activities (figures 1 and 2) present an average of 31847.91 with a standard error of 8162.452.

Working hypothesis: the distribution of scores is considered normal and, therefore, parametric tests will be applied. The extreme values of the distribution, although they are in very small numbers, change the PSYCHO-SOCIAL VIEW JOURNAL (2/2021)

appearance of the histogram, by inducing a positive asymmetry, being still statistically important. The concentration of a large number of scores around the average produces a certain leptocurticity of the distribution, due to the related phenomena in the Romanian economy. The logarithm of the values obtained, according to the universally accepted statistical rules, allowed to balance the distribution according to the normal Gauss-Laplace curve.

Figure 1. Histogram for pentru Professional, Scientific and Technical Activities; administrative and support activities

Source: Author according to Eurostat - Business Demography Statistics

At a first analysis, the distribution curve is relatively symmetrically central, and the scores around the average are very concentrated, with the appearance of leptocurticity, although the distribution is unimodal.

Figure 2. Chart of the Q-Q normal plot distribution for Professional, Scientific and Technical Activities; administrative and support activities after logarithm

Source: Author according to Eurostat - Business Demography Statistics

The normal Q-Q plot test, after logarithm, shows a distribution of real scores around normal values, represented by the oblique line in the graph, which corresponds to a normal distribution.

The Q-Q detrended plot test, regarding the dispersion of empirical scores compared to normal, represented by the right with the score $z = 0$ for the mean and standard deviation 1, after logarithm, shows that they fall within a standard deviation, corresponding to a normal distribution.

By logarithm, the scores obtained were subjected to a statistical processing, after which all the factors involved in the study were taken into account, to obtain data as close as possible to the reality recorded in Romania, even if the measures taken in the economy unbalanced the distribution of scores. short period of time.

The importance of these tests is given by the need to carefully observe the influences of certain factors in the evolution of the sectors Professional, scientific and technical activities; administrative and support activities. Following the application of normality tests, after logarithmization, the null hypothesis must be rejected and the working hypothesis can be analyzed. The descriptive and inferential analysis will be done considering the distribution of scores within normal limits, according to the working hypothesis, for which the parametric tests are applied.

The central trend for this sector in the analyzed period shows that the population of mountainous Romania of the active enterprises in the studied sector increased from 2008 to 2018. In the analyzed period, the hypothesis of activity intensification was verified.

The statistics, presented above, and the histogram confirm the high agglomeration and the development trend of this sector in Romania. At the same time, statistics confirm the intensification of the growth rate of this sector. This sector could be one of the most valuable for mountain Romania.

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EDUCATION, HUMAN HEALTH AND SOCIAL ASSISTANCE ACTIVITIES OF THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN ACTIVITIES

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Abstract

However, if learning institutions, teachers and politicians want to strengthen lifelong learning capacity, there are good reasons to look more closely at how different approaches to entrepreneurship can contribute in different ways to its promotion and use. There is no privileged context for entrepreneurship in higher education, nor is there a way to teach or learn entrepreneurship, nor is there a common vision of what should be included in concepts such as entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial learning.

Keywords: Romanian mountain activities; mountain statistic; education, human health and social assistance activities

Introduction:

Nestled amidst the picturesque landscapes and majestic peaks, the Romanian mountains not only boast natural beauty but also harbor activities crucial for the well-being and development of the local communities. This article explores the symbiotic relationship between education, human health, and social assistance activities in the Romanian mountain regions, shedding light on the initiatives that contribute to the holistic growth of individuals and communities.

Education Initiatives:

Education stands as the cornerstone for the prosperity of any community, and the Romanian mountains are no exception. The region has witnessed commendable efforts to provide quality education, ensuring that the younger generation has access to opportunities for intellectual growth. Despite the challenges posed by the mountainous terrain, schools and educational institutions have emerged as beacons of knowledge, fostering a sense of curiosity and ambition among the youth.

Initiatives such as scholarship programs, educational outreach, and vocational training contribute to breaking barriers and empowering individuals to pursue their dreams. In the Romanian mountains, where the landscape can sometimes pose challenges for educational access, these initiatives play a crucial role in bridging the gap and ensuring that every child has the chance to learn and thrive.

Human Health and Wellness:

The well-being of mountain communities is intricately linked to human health, and initiatives focusing on healthcare play a pivotal role in ensuring a robust and resilient society. Health centers, clinics, and awareness programs are vital components of the healthcare infrastructure in the Romanian mountains. They not only provide medical assistance but also promote preventive measures and health education.

With the challenges posed by the mountainous geography, health initiatives often incorporate innovative solutions such as mobile clinics and telemedicine to reach remote areas. These efforts contribute to a healthier population, fostering a sense of security and trust within the communities.

Results:

A study conducted in Sweden concluded that, regardless of perspective, entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial learning offer new opportunities to improve learning among students. The study also suggests that any political or scientific initiative must recognize the diversity of entrepreneurship education and choose different approaches depending on what is to be achieved. Talking about a special form of pedagogy may seem difficult

Hoppe, Magnus & Westerberg, Mats & Leffler, Eva. (2017) Educational approaches to entrepreneurship in higher education: A view from the Swedish horizon. *Education and Training*. 59. 751- 767. 10.1108 / ET-12-2016-0177).

The studies of Blenker et al. suggests that entrepreneurship creates new opportunities for wealth creation in society by establishing an integrative space in which the reflective capacity to cope with opportunities can be improved. An integrative framework, which brings together the ideas of entrepreneurial behavior, entrepreneurial university and entrepreneurial learning, can be useful for professors of university management and entrepreneurship (Blenker, Per & Dreisler, Poul & Faergemann, Helle & Kjeldsen, John (2008). for developing entrepreneurship education in a

university context. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business - Int J Enterpren Small Bus.* 5. 10.1504 / IJESB.2008.015953).

A study by Hatak & Zhou supports previous theorizing in demonstrating that the mental and physical health of entrepreneurs leads to higher levels of entrepreneurial success and subjective well-being. In addition to their own health, entrepreneurs report higher levels of subjective well-being when their spouse is mentally and physically healthy. No support was found for the hypothesis that a better mental health of the husband would be linked to a greater monetary success in entrepreneurship. This result is contrary to previous research which failed to take both partners into account in a cohabitation dyad. Divergent results for dyadic health effects in terms of monetary success thus have important implications for health and human capital research in entrepreneurship (Volume: 45 issue: 1, page (s): 18-42, Article first published online: August 13 , 2019; Issue published: January 1, 2021, Isabella Hatak, Haibo Zhou).

The research conducted by Prag et al. on a number of 37 studies that analyzed 87 relationships between entrepreneurship and economic results indicate some advantages and disadvantages of entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurs create more jobs than large companies, compared to their size, but the quality of jobs created by entrepreneurs is lower. This is due, among other things, to the fact that entrepreneurs hire people with lower

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levels of human capital than other companies. Entrepreneurs pay lower wages, but also offer fewer benefits. However, it seems that entrepreneurs offer their employees other intangible benefits, because their employees are more satisfied with their jobs (less paid and less secure) than the employees of large companies. On the innovation side, entrepreneurs do not spend more on research and development than large companies. They produce fewer patents, fewer new products and fewer technologies. Moreover, the percentage of radical innovations is lower among entrepreneurial firms. However, the efficiency with which innovations are produced seems to be higher and so is the quality of innovations, as measured by the number of patents. Entrepreneurs market innovations to a greater extent, but when adopting innovations, they have a lower score compared to large companies. Additionally, entrepreneurs have higher levels of job satisfaction than employees (Prague, Mirjam & Praag, C. & Versloot, Peter. (2007). What Is the Value of Entrepreneurship? A Review of Recent Research. *Small Business Economics*. 29. 351-382. 10.1007 / s11187-007-9074-x.).

Statistics for Education; human health and social assistance activities (figures 1 and 2) with an average of 8261.64 with a standard error of 4455.942.

At a first analysis, the distribution curve is relatively symmetrically central, and the scores around the average are very concentrated, with the appearance of leptocurticity, although the distribution is unimodal.

Figure 1. Histogram for Education, human health and social assistance activities

Source: Author according to Eurostat - Business Demography Statistics

Figura 2. Chart of the Q-Q normal plot distribution for Education, human health and social assistance activities after logarithm

Source: Author according to Eurostat - Business Demography Statistics

Entrepreneurship takes place within the new trends of social policy: active social policies. Innovation is the key element of entrepreneurship, which can help us in the reconstruction of social assistance intervention. However, being perceived as a growth mechanism, it poses to humanity (especially professionals) a set of unknown moral, ethical and political issues. (Jesus, Antonela Spínola. (2016). Social Work and Social Entrepreneurship: A new framework for practice?. March 2016. Conference: 6th European Conference for Social Work Research)

Social Assistance and Community Support:

In the Romanian mountains, where close-knit communities thrive, social assistance activities play a central role in ensuring that no one is left behind. Programs addressing poverty, social inequality, and community development initiatives have been instrumental in creating a support system for residents.

Initiatives ranging from job training programs to community development projects uplift the socio-economic fabric of the region. Social workers and community organizers work hand in hand with residents to identify needs and implement solutions that enhance the overall quality of life.

Conclusion:

Education, human health, and social assistance activities form the bedrock of a thriving and resilient society. In the Romanian mountains, these initiatives not only overcome geographical challenges but also contribute to the preservation of cultural heritage and the sustainable development of communities. As we appreciate the breathtaking landscapes, let us also celebrate the endeavors that nurture minds, care for bodies, and build strong, interconnected communities in the heart of the Romanian mountains.

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